

A PROVENANCE QUESTIONS

This section presents representative questions associated to each of the use cases defined in Section 4.1. Here, we relate them to the components of the provenance taxonomy defined in Section 4.

U1: Workflow development

- (1) What is the influence of a different model architecture on performance? **SW1, SW2, WF1, WF2**
- (2) What is the influence of removing input feature X on performance? **WF1, SC2**
- (3) What is the influence of including filtering step X on performance? **WF1, SC2**
- (4) What is the influence of ... on training time? **EX1**
- (5) What is the influence of a different training set on performance? **D1**

A.1 U2: Publishing the workflow

- (1) What are all the resources which contributed to this research (and should be cited)? **D1, SW1, WF1, ENV3**
- (2) What are all the input data I used? **D4**
- (3) Which software was used in this workflow? **SW1**
- (4) I reused an existing CWL *CommandLineTool* description. How do I give credit to the original authors? **WF1**
- (5) I wrote a CWL *CommandLineTool* description for existing software. How do I cite it? **SW1**
- (6) I reused a custom, unpublished script made by one of my collaborators. How do I give credit to the original authors? **SW1**
- (7) I wrote a custom script based on existing code. How do I give credit to the original authors? **SW1**
- (8) I reused a Dockerfile or Docker container which was written or built by someone else. How do I give credit to the original authors? **ENV3**
- (9) Which of my colleagues contributed to this workflow to whom I should give credit and/or propose as co-authors? What were their contributions? **WF1, EX4**
- (10) From which workflow(s) was this workflow derived? **WF1**

A.2 U3: Understanding the workflow

- (1) What is the goal of this analysis? What was the hypothesis of this experiment? **SC3**
- (2) Why was this step included? **SC1**
- (3) Why was this combination of steps chosen? **SC1**
- (4) Why was this set of values chosen as inputs for this workflow execution? **SC3**
- (5) How was this figure from the paper generated? **D4**
- (6) Why were these input settings chosen? **SC3**
- (7) What is the interpretation of this (intermediate) output? **SC2**
- (8) Which input features were used for the model? **WF1**
- (9) Which related tasks were predicted by the model? **WF1**
- (10) What are the values of PSP19 for each amino acid type? **SC2**
- (11) What was the performance of the model? **SC2**
- (12) What was model architecture? **SW1, SW2**

- (13) Where can I find more information about BioDL dataset? **D1**
- (14) How were UniProt IDs mapped to PDB IDs? **WF1**
- (15) Which SABDab query was used to generate the summary file? **SC2, D1**
- (16) Which query was issued to PDB? **SC2, D1**
- (17) Which UniProt IDs are part of BioDL? **D1**

A.3 U4: Reproducing the workflow

- (1) Which HHBlits reference database was used? Which version? **D1**
- (2) Where can I download HHBlits reference database? (It was not stored in the RO because of its large size.) **D3**
- (3) Which version of HHBlits was used? **SW1, ENV1**
- (4) Which software (and their versions) was installed on the system? **ENV1**
- (5) I pulled a Docker image. Is this the same as which was used in the original analysis? **ENV3**
- (6) Original author used Dockerfile. Is the image I built on a rerun the same as the one in the original analysis? **ENV3**
- (7) What are resource requirements as specified in the workflow description? **WF3**
- (8) How many CPUs are required for this step? **WF3, EX2**
- (9) How much memory is necessary for this step? **WF3, EX2**
- (10) How much memory was used in the original run? **EX2**
- (11) Does this step need network access? **WF3, EX2**
- (12) Which CPU/GPU was installed? **ENV2**
- (13) How long does this step take? **WF3, EX1**
- (14) What was the last modification date of this input file? **D2**
- (15) Which Python version was used in this step? **SW1, ENV1**
- (16) When was PDB queried? **EX1**
- (17) When was SABDab queried? **EX1**
- (18) Which format does the PDB batch download script need? **WF2**
- (19) The CWL *CommandLineTool* description did not describe all parameters of this command-line program. Which values were used for the other parameters? **WF2**

A.4 U5: Model as a web service

- (1) Which protein sequences were in the training set? **D1**
- (2) Which proteins had epitope annotations? **D1**
- (3) For which proteins did I make epitope predictions? **D1**
- (4) How should I cite this tool? **WF1**

B INPUT ANNOTATION EXAMPLES

B.1 Annotations supported by CWL Standards v1.2

B.1.1 Annotations for a non-FAIR file. When the dataset is not FAIR, the download or modification date (*line 7*) can serve as an alternative for version. The URL of the remote file is used as an alternative to a persistent identifier (*line 3*).

```
1 unFAIR_file:
2   class: File
3   location: https://www.ibi.vu.nl/downloads/PIPENN/PIPENN/BioDL-Datasets/prepared_biolip_win_p_testing.csv
4   format: http://edamontology.org/format_3752 # csv
5   s:additionalType: s:Dataset
6   s:name: "BioDL test set"
7   s:dateModified: "2021-08-02" # an alternative to version
8   s:citation:
9     s:identifier: https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btac071
10    s:license: https://spdx.org/licenses/GPL-3.0-or-later.html
11    s:description: "BioDL test set containing only protein-protein interactions."
```

B.2 Annotations requiring extension of CWL Standards

B.2.1 Annotation of a dataset merged from two other datasets. In this example, a dataset is constructed from two other datasets (*lines 4-6*). Here, the instrument is not a tool but a function (*line 7*).

```
1 cwlprov:prov:
2   merge_action:
3     s:additionalType: s:Action
4     s:object:
5       - dataset1
6       - dataset2
7     s:instrument: pd.merge(dataset1, dataset2, on = "ID", how = "inner")
8     s:result: merged_dataset
9     s:description: "Imported both datasets as pandas dataframes, performed inner merge and saved as csv."
10
11 merged_dataset:
12   class: File
13   location: path://path/to/file.csv
```

B.3 Annotations for epitope prediction workflow

Below, we show how we applied our annotation scheme to the input file for our example workflow. We represented the download action which produced the *sabdad_summary_file* (*lines 3-16*). If files were not downloaded during workflow execution, we supplied the URL to the dataset using *s:distribution* (*line 69*). Every file has a citation (*s:citation*), consisting of the DOI of the primary publication. Finally, we supplied EDAM annotations to each *File* and *Directory* input (*lines 29, 44, 58, 72*) and annotated the workflow run (*line 78*).

```
1 cwlprov:prov:
2   sabdad_search:
3     s:additionalType: s:SearchAction
4     s:query: "All structures"
5     s:endTime: 2022-05-27
6     s:object:
7       s:additionalType: s:DataCatalog
8       s:name: "Structural Antibody Database"
9       s:citation:
10        s:identifier: https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab1050
11        s:result: sabdad_summary_file
12        s:description: "Search Action for metadata on antibody-antigen complexes in SABDab"
13        s:additionalType: edam:operation_0339 # structure database search
14
15 pdb_search_api_query:
16   class: File
17   location: path://path/to/pdb_query.json
```

```

18  format: iana:application/json
19  s:description: "Input query for PDB search API."
20  s:additionalType:
21  - edam:data_3786 # Query script
22
23  sabdab_summary_file:
24  class: File
25  path: path://path/to/sabdab_summary_all_20220527.tsv
26  format: iana:text/tab-separated-values
27  s:description: "Summary file downloaded from SABDAB database, containing metadata for all structures."
28  s:additionalType:
29  - edam:data_2080 # database search results
30  - s:Dataset
31
32  biobl_train_dataset:
33  class: File
34  location: https://www.ibi.vu.nl/downloads/PIPENN/PIPENN/BioDL-Datasets/prepared_biolip_win_p_training.csv
35  format: http://edamontology.org/format_3752 # csv
36  s:description: "BioDL training set containing PPI annotations for protein sequences (UniProt IDs)"
37  s:name: "BioDL training dataset"
38  s:dateModified: 2021-08-04
39  s:citation:
40    s:identifier: https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btac071
41  s:license: https://spdx.org/licenses/GPL-3.0-or-later.html
42  s:additionalType:
43  - s:Dataset
44  - edam:data_1277 # protein features
45
46  biobl_test_dataset:
47  class: File
48  location: https://www.ibi.vu.nl/downloads/PIPENN/PIPENN/BioDL-Datasets/prepared_biolip_win_p_testing.csv
49  format: http://edamontology.org/format_3752 # csv
50  s:description: "BioDL test set containing PPI annotations for protein sequences (UniProt IDs)."
51  s:name: "BioDL test dataset"
52  s:dateModified: 2021-08-04
53  s:citation:
54    s:identifier: https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btac071
55  s:license: https://spdx.org/licenses/GPL-3.0-or-later.html
56  s:additionalType:
57  - s:Dataset
58  - edam:data_1277 # protein features
59
60  hhblits_db_dir:
61  class: Directory
62  location: path://path/to/uniclust30_2018_08/
63  s:citation:
64    s:identifier: https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.1818
65  s:name: "uniclust30_2018_08_hhsuite"
66  s:version: "2018_08"
67  s:description: "Directory containing HHBlits reference database."
68  s:license: https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0
69  s:distribution: https://wwwuser.gwdg.de/~compbiol/uniclust/2018_08/uniclust30_2018_08_hhsuite.tar.gz
70  s:additionalType:
71  - s:Dataset
72  - edam:data_0955 # data index
73
74  hhblits_db_name: "uniclust30_2018"

```

```
75
76 hhblits_n_iterations: 1
77
78 s:description: "Demonstration run of epitope prediction workflow. Some steps are emulated, so the results of
↳ the workflow are not yet biologically meaningful."
79
80 $namespaces:
81   iana: "https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/"
82   s: "https://schema.org/"
83   edam: "http://edamontology.org/"
84
85 $schemas:
86 - https://schema.org/version/latest/schemaorg-current-https.rdf
87 - https://edamontology.org/EDAM_1.25.owl
```